

This document contains all the codes used to implement the study “*Contrasting Soil Temperature Responses to Extreme Rainfall in Permafrost Regions With Implications for Permafrost Thaw.*”

It includes three annotated files, which highlight the following:

- (1) the specific functions to be achieved, and
- (2) the corresponding code file names implementing these functions.

Therefore, the annotated files should be read first.

It should be noted that the code files referenced in the three annotated documents are located in different directories:

- (1) *F:\ Code*
- (2) *F:\ Code\Code of Influence Pattern*
- (3) *F:\ Code\Round2 Before Submit*

Table1. The **first** supplementary information document.

<p>1. Data Integration</p> <p>1.1 China: Integration of air temperature, rainfall, and soil temperature data from monitoring sites</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Read early and late-period air temperature (<i>China_Read_Tem.m</i>) • Read early and late-period rainfall (<i>China_Read_Pre.m</i>) • Read early and late-period soil temperature (<i>China_Read_ST.m</i>) • Identify sites to be included (<i>China_Site_Used.m</i>) • Integrate air temperature, rainfall, and soil temperature data (<i>China_Combine_Tem_Pre_ST.m</i>) • Export data for sites located in continuous and discontinuous permafrost regions (<i>China_Site_Choosed.m</i>) <p>1.2 Russia: Integration of air temperature, rainfall, and soil temperature data from monitoring sites</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Select sites providing all three variables (<i>Russia_Site_Used.m</i>) • Read air temperature and rainfall (<i>Russia_Read_Tem_Pre.m</i>) • Read soil temperature (<i>Russia_Read_ST.m</i>) • Integrate air temperature, rainfall, and soil temperature data (<i>Russia_Combine_Tem_Pre_ST.m</i>) • Export data for sites located in continuous and discontinuous permafrost regions (<i>Russia_Site_Choosed.m</i>) <p>1.3 United States: Integration of air temperature, rainfall, and soil temperature data from monitoring sites</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Read data from USA SCAN (<i>USA_Read_SCAN.m</i>) • Read data from USA SNOTEL (<i>USA_Read_SNOTEL.m</i>) • Read data from 17 USGS sites (<i>USGS_Read_17sites.m, USGS_Read_17sites_New.m</i>)
<p>2. Calculation of Relative Variation Ratio</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2.1 Calculate the relative variation ratio for China (<i>China_Cal_Vrel.m</i>) • 2.2 Calculate the relative variation ratio for Russia (<i>Russia_Cal_Vrel.m</i>) • 2.3 Calculate the relative variation ratio for the United States (<i>USA_Cal_Vrel.m, USGS_Cal_Vrel.m</i>)

3. Hierarchical Linear Regression Analysis of the Effects of Extreme Rainfall on Soil Temperature and Thaw Depth

- 3.1 China (*China_HLR.m, China_HLR.R*)
- 3.2 Russia (*Russia_HLR.m, Russia_HLR.R*)
- 3.3 United States (*USA_HLR.m, USA_HLR.R*)
- 3.4 Alaska (*USGS_HLR.m, USGS_HLR.R*)

4. Delta T Method

- 4.1 China (*China_Verify_Assumption_1.m*)
- 4.2 Russia (*Russia_Verify_Assumption_1.m*)
- 4.3 United States (*USA_Verify_Assumption_1.m*)
- 4.4 Alaska (*USGS_Verify_Assumption_1.m*)

5. Calculation of Continentality and Oceanicity Indices

- 5.1 Calculate the continentality and oceanicity indices for China (*China_Cal_CCI_KOI.m*)
- 5.2 Calculate the continentality and oceanicity indices for Russia (*Russia_Cal_CCI_KOI.m*)
- 5.3 Calculate the continentality and oceanicity indices for the United States (*USA_Cal_CCI_KOI.m, USGS_Cal_CCI_KOI.m*)
- 5.4 Analyze the relative variation ratio based on the continentality and oceanicity indices (*Analysis_CCI_KOI_Vrel.m*)

Table2. The **second** supplementary information document.

- Export the latitude and longitude of monitoring sites in China, Russia, the United States, and Alaska (*Influence_Pattern_Lat_Lon.m*)
- Download ERA5-Land data for the selected sites (GEE: *Influence_Pattern_Download_ERA5_Data*)
- Check ERA5-Land rainfall data for quality issues (*Influence_Pattern_Check_ERA5.m*)
- Integrate ERA5-Land data (*Influence_Pattern_Integrate_ERA5.m*)
- Compile results of relative variation ratio, hierarchical linear regression, and ΔT at 20 cm depth for 131 sites (*Influence_Pattern_Integrate_Three_Method_20cm.m*)
- Compile results of relative variation ratio, hierarchical linear regression, and ΔT at 5 cm depth for 131 sites (*Influence_Pattern_Integrate_Three_Method_5cm.m*)
- Perform principal component analysis (PCA) based on the compiled ERA5 data and the results from the three methods (*Influence_Pattern_PCA.m*)
- Conduct PCA for all sites (*Influence_Pattern_PCA_Overall.m*)
- Conduct PCA by climate zones (*Influence_Pattern_PCA_Diff_Clim_Zone.m*)
- Generate figures for the discussion section (“Paper 2”) at 20 cm depth (*Influence_Pattern_Paper2_20cm.m*)
- Generate figures for the discussion section (“Paper 2”) at 5 cm depth (*Influence_Pattern_Paper2_5cm.m*)
- Calculate the contribution of environmental factors to the response variables using Rdacca.hp (*Influence_Pattern_Rdacca.m, Influence_Pattern_Rdacca.R*)

Table3. The **third** supplementary information document.

- Demonstrate shallow cooling and deep warming based on the relative variation ratio (**Impact_Of_Extreme_Rainfall_Method_1.m**)
- Demonstrate shallow cooling and deep warming based on hierarchical linear regression (**Impact_Of_Extreme_Rainfall_Method_2.m**)
- Demonstrate shallow cooling and deep warming based on ΔT (**Impact_Of_Extreme_Rainfall_Method_3.m**)
- Illustrate regional heterogeneity of the initial warming layer using the relative variation ratio (**First_Warming_Layer_Method_1.m**)
- Illustrate regional heterogeneity of the initial warming layer using hierarchical linear regression (**First_Warming_Layer_Method_2.m**)
- Illustrate regional heterogeneity of the initial warming layer using ΔT (**First_Warming_Layer_Method_3.m**)
- Classify precipitation types based on air temperature (**Precipitation_Class.m**)
- Prepare data for visualizing the dominance and sequentiality of extreme rainfall effects (**Visualizing_Dominance_And_Sequentiality.m**)
- Explain the initial warming layer based on vegetation coverage and soil organic carbon (**Initial_Warming_Layer_Vegetation_SOC.m**)

Notes: These code files contain comments, which are written in Chinese. If needed, the comments can be translated into English or other languages using tools such as ChatGPT or Kimi. When running the code, only the file paths need to be updated.